

D15.2 – Dissemination and Communication Package RP1

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Type

- R** Document report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.
- Other**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN** Sensitive, restricted under conditions set out in the Grant Agreement
- CI** Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 1001/844/EC

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Report

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Acronyms and abbreviations

D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
GA	Grant Agreement
H4C	Hubs for Circularity
M	Month
RP1	First Reporting Period

Acronyms used to identify consortium members

Beneficiary Ref.	Acronym	Organisation
B1	EUCORE	EU CORE CONSULTING SRL
B2	POLIMI	POLITECNICO DI MILANO
B3	LUT	LAPPEENRANNAN-LAHDEN TEKNILLINEN YLIOPISTO LUT
B4	VTT	TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY
B5	ELCOGEN	AKTSIASELTS ELCOGEN
B6	ICODOS	ICODOS GMBH
B7	ECODESIGN	ECODESIGN COMPANY ENGINEERING & MANAGEMENT CONSULTANCY GMBH
B8	INERIS	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT INDUSTRIEL ET DES RISQUES - INERIS
B9	WOOD	WOOD ITALIANA SRL
B10	RIC	CENTRUM BADAN I INNOWACJI PROAKADEMIA STOWARZYSZENIE
B11	UNI	UNI - ENTE ITALIANO DI NORMAZIONE
B12	ELCOY	ELCOGEN OY

1. Publishable executive summary

The BeBOP D15.2, *Dissemination and Communication Package RP1*, compiles all dissemination and communication materials and activities implemented and completed during the first reporting period (M1-M18) of the project.

As far as the materials are concerned, this report provides an overview of the physical outputs of the communication and dissemination materials designed to foster the project's visual identity with the intent of creating branding affiliation and loyalty. These include the design of the logo, the templates and the promotional materials in general (e.g. brochure, posters, folders, etc). All of them have been produced by EUCORE with the support and inputs from all the partners. All the materials are currently in English, but in the following months the brochure will be translated into the consortium members' languages: French, Italian, German, Polish, Estonian and Finnish.

All the materials detailed in this document were produced in accordance with the procedures and project visual identity of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D15.1) submitted in M6.

In addition, this report presents a summary of all the activities performed to disseminate and communicate the BeBOP project and its results, including dissemination events where BeBOP participated, publications, communication activities, participation in external events and liaison activities.

As a result, the deliverable is a reflection of the work carried out by all project partners in support of WP15, since dissemination and communication are regarded as strategic activities to engage all the target groups relevant to BeBOP: Research and scientific community, industrial stakeholders, policymakers, regulatory organisations, press, general public (etc.)¹.

While this deliverable thoroughly outlines all the developed Dissemination and Communication materials, channels and events, its primary goal is to assemble a "Dissemination and Communication Package" featuring resources and a summary of outreach efforts. It does not serve as an assessment of these endeavours, as they will be addressed in the Technical report (part B) of the first reporting period (RP1), which will include KPI's and event participant numbers.

¹ Refer to the second version of D15.1, *Dissemination and Communication Plan*, for more details on the BeBOP's relevant target groups.

2. BeBOP visual identity: Logo and the EU compliance

The final logo was selected in November 2024 by the consortium among several options delivered by the Graphic agency collaborating with EUCORE, and it conveys the following main concepts:

- *BeBOP's circularity, hence the circle arrow*
- *CO₂-neutrality, given by the green colour*
- *Highlight the raw materials to be used in the BeBOP processes.*

In particular, the logo aims to highlight the raw materials used in the process and the circularity aspects, not only in keeping carbon in methanol, but in closing all the loops of material and energy flows in the BeBOP solution.

Three versions of the logo have been developed (see Figures below): **i)** simple logo only including the acronym; **ii)** the logo and the acronym with also the inclusion of the pay-off: '*Biomass to bio/e-methanol by SOEC based process*'; i.e. the abbreviation of the complete name of the project and the core objective expected from its implementation; **iii)** the last option (graphic logo, acronym and pay-off) is also available in black and white, meant to be used on coloured backgrounds.

Figure 1. BeBOP's available logo(s)

As the logo represents the Project’s visual identity, it shall be included in all the project communication, dissemination and exploitation outputs, including leaflets, roll-ups, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, website, publications, and materials for internal and external events. To simplify and standardise the use of the logo by all the partners, a Brand Book has been shared on the project repository (Teams). This manual contains all the main instructions on how the logo should be used, including the exact Pantone colours, scaling measures, and information on different logo stails are to be used depending on the background (see figure below).

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS: MINIMUM DIMENSIONS

When the logo size is reduced below 5 cm, the legibility of the payoff may be compromised. Therefore, when using the logo at reduced sizes, the payoff is removed, and an adapted version of the logo without the payoff is used.

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS: COLORS

The primary colors used for the logo design are grey, green, and orange.

Figure 2. Extractions from the Brand Book on how to use the logo

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS: PRIMARY FONT

SuiGenerisRG-Regular
 ABCDEFGHILMNOPQRSTUVWXYZJK
 abcdefghilmnopqrstuvwxyzjk
 1234567890îè+ùàò
 -.,<\|'!"£\$%&/()=?^*~°ç_~;#|}€€@

Furthermore, in compliance with art. 17 of the BeBOP Grant Agreement (GA), all communication and dissemination materials must also include the:

- i) **The disclaimer** agreed with the PO, i.e. *'Funded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101178117. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.'* and
- ii) **The EU emblem and funding statement** with an appropriate prominence. The EU emblem can be displayed either horizontally or vertically, as indicated in the figure to follow:

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

Figure 3. EU emblem(s)

Therefore, each BeBOP's outputs, to be considered eligible and in compliance with the GA obligations on communication, dissemination and visibility, must include the following complete acknowledgement as displayed in the figure below:

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101178117. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 4. BeBOP complete acknowledgement

3. Templates

To foster BeBOP’s visual identity and to harmonise its appearance in terms of outputs, reporting and presentations, the consortium agreed to design three different templates:

- a) Template for writing all the project Deliverables;
- b) Template for Policy briefs and general cooperation reports;
- c) Template to be used for any BeBOP’s PowerPoint presentation.

Below are displayed the above-mentioned graphic templates:

A) **Template for project Deliverables.** The template displayed below shall be used for drafting all BeBOP’s Deliverables should they be classified with a public or sensitive dissemination level.

The figure shows three pages of the BeBOP Deliverable template. The first page is the cover page, featuring the BeBOP logo and the text 'Deliverable Number: Deliverable title'. The second page is the metadata page, containing fields for 'Deliverable reference number', 'Work package number', 'Due date deliverable', and 'Actual submission date'. It also includes a table for 'Contributors' with columns for Name, Organisation, and Email, and a section for 'Dissemination Level' with options like 'Public, fully accessible' and 'Sensitive, restricted under conditions'. The third page is the beneficiary information page, with sections for 'Lead beneficiary', 'Contributing beneficiaries', and 'Internal reviewer(s)'. Each page includes the BeBOP logo and the text 'Deliverable Number: Deliverable title' at the top.

The figure shows three pages of the BeBOP Deliverable template. The first page is the report page, featuring a table with columns for 'Project Title', 'Action Acronym', 'Action Number', 'Deliverable Identifier', 'Deliverable Title', 'Authors', 'Lead Beneficiary', 'Deliverable Type', 'Dissemination Level', 'Format', 'Due Month and Date', and 'Keywords'. The second page is the 'Table of content' page, listing sections like '1. Publishable executive summary', '2. Introduction', '3. Introduction subtitle', '4. 1. Header', '4.1. Header 2/3/4/5/6/7/8/9', '4.2. Header 2', and '5. Conclusions'. The third page is the '1. Publishable executive summary' page, containing a large block of placeholder text. Each page includes the BeBOP logo and the text 'Deliverable Number: Deliverable title' at the top.

Figure 5. BeBOP’s Deliverable template

B) Template for Policy briefs and general cooperation reports. This template is to be used for other types of documents not strictly related to the project, such as Policy briefs and/or liaison activities.

Figure 6. BeBOP's template for Policy briefs and general cooperation report

C) PowerPoint presentation template to be used in all project presentations:

Figure 7. BeBOP's PowerPoint presentations template

4. Promotional Materials

During the First Reporting Period (RP1), following the definition of the BeBOP’s visual identity, several promotional materials have been designed to strengthen the impact of the project’s Dissemination and Communication (D&C) campaigns. These include: the project Poster, Roll-up, brochure, Factsheet, overview, business card, block notes, template for event’s invitations, background for calls, folder, postcard and stickers. Except for the project overview presentation, all the promotional materials above are available for download on the BeBOP website: <https://www.bebop-project.eu/results-and-publications/>.

4.1. Project Poster and Roll-Up

Designed using Canva, the BeBOP project poster can be adapted and personalised by partners according to the event and/or activities to be presented. **Figure 8** below shows the poster template and the general BeBOP poster, which has been used on different occasions to provide a general overview of the project. The intention behind creating the project poster was to boost brand recognition for both internal and external events. Although it can be printed in various dimensions and contains similar information to the roll-up, it was designed with the objective of making it easier to carry while being more compact and lightweight compared to the project roll-up.

Figure 8. BeBOP’s poster template and general BeBOP’s overview poster

A 200 cm x 80 cm roll-up has been designed as one of the most relevant tools for BeBOP branding, controlling visibility and message clarity at events and conferences. Designed with a similar structure to the poster template, it includes all the main information of the project, such as the logo, the map and logos of all the consortium partners, a brief description of the BeBOP concept and goals and a visual and schematic explanation of BeBOP's solution. Furthermore, the QR codes located at the bottom of the roll-up allow users to easily browse the BeBOP website and social media profiles using mobile devices.

The Roll-Up was printed out and displayed for the first time during the First [BeBOP Dissemination Event](#), held in Milan on 07/10/2025.

Figure 9. BeBOP's project roll-up

4.2. BeBOP's Brochure and Factsheet

BeBOP's brochure has been designed as a tri-fold of 45 cm x 15,4 cm when open.

The brochure was created as a strategic communication tool aimed at translating complex project information into a clear and structured narrative available to the general public. It includes the following set of information:

1. The main figures of the project: brief descriptions and goals, start date, budget and PERT;
2. The challenges in the methanol production from the biomass sector compared to the solution(s) and goal tackled by BeBOP technology;
3. A general overview of the main technological implementation fields;
4. Inputs on why specific actors would be interested in the deployment of BeBOP, alongside the consortium map and the QR-code to access the website.

The English version of the brochure is available for download on BeBOP's [website](#) and on the BeBOP community in [Zenodo](#), while partners have access to either printable or web versions in the shared repository. Translations to other consortium languages (French, Italian, German, Polish, Estonian and Finnish) are in progress and will be finalised within the next few months.

Current challenges and BeBOP solution
Low carbon efficiency in conventional biomass-to-methanol systems due to carbon losses and limited oxygen management.

TRL6: 20 kW biomass-scale pilot plant

BeBOP INNOVATION: Integration of SOEC into the syngas line to remove excess oxygen electrochemically, improving methanol synthesis efficiency.

Why should I be interested in BeBOP?

- I am a policy maker! It would be great to know how this system could be integrated in the energy transition and what are the gaps that we have to fill in.
- I am a scientist and I'm always interested in new technologies to overcome the current knowledge on biomass to methanol production.
- I am a farmer! It would be fantastic to know which kind of wood discard could be used as a by-product to produce energy!
- I am an investor and as someone who is interested in investing in green technologies with high returns and low risks, I believe this is an excellent opportunity!
- Hi, I'm the owner of a methanol plant, and it would be great to know how to reduce CO₂ emissions while decreasing our overall costs.
- I am a high school teacher and I'm very interested in raising awareness on a sustainable way to produce biofuels and green chemicals from biomass in order to inspire and educate the new generation!

Project partners: VTT, Ecogen, E.ON Energy, Ecosoc, Ecocarbon, UNL, wood.

Find out more about the project

BeBOP is a Horizon Europe project aimed at demonstrating a highly efficient and circular biomass-to-e-methanol system. The project integrates a Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell (SOEC) with a biomass gasifier and a methanol synthesis unit, creating a low-emission, flexible and scalable Power-Biomass-to-X (PBtX) configuration.

Project Structure

- 01 • Gasification system and BeBOP integration
- 02 • BeBOP SOEC system-laboratory and industrial application
- 03 • Design and planned implementation of SOE and syngas compression unit
- 04 • The Digitalization framework of the BeBOP system
- 05 • The BeBOP 3D-Printed Methanol Reactor and Synthesis Integration
- 06 • Leaching and Recovery of solid resources from gasification
- 07 • Circularity of the BeBOP system
- 08 • BeBOP system analysis
- 09 • Standardizing framework for BeBOP System
- 10 • Exploiting, Communicating, and Disseminating the BeBOP Innovation

Project details: Start Date: October 1st, 2024; Budget/EU Contribution: € 11,666,415.71; Number of Partners: 12; Project duration: 48 months; Coordinator: EuCore Consulting S.r.l.

Figure 10. BeBOP's project brochure

The BeBOP's Factsheet is instead a concise and data-focused communication instrument designed to present BeBOP's essential information. The language used and the information included are more technical than those of the brochure (see more details in the Figure below).

BeBOP
Biomass to bio/E-methanol by Breakthrough SOEC-based Process: the BeBOP innovation

PROJECT AND GENERAL OBJECTIVES

The Horizon Europe BeBOP project aims to industrially deploy a disruptive, **digital process-intensified, ultra-high resource efficient and flexible biomass power-to-methanol plant**, that can transform the chemical sector, while showcasing a **first-of-its-kind complete TRL6 pilot plant**, ready to be scaled up and replicated by the European biomass-based industry.

CURRENT CHALLENGES

Climate change is calling for **cleaner energy sources** in the electric, industrial and mobility sectors and **higher efficiency in the use of resources**.

THE BeBOP SOLUTION

BeBOP is a disruptive Power Biomass to X (PBtX) system.

- Integrated SOEC for syngas upgrading
- Electrochemical separation of excess oxygen to enhance bio-methanol production
- 100% biogenic carbon usage
- Reduction of environmental impact & carbon footprint
- TRL6 pilot demonstration – 20 kW biomass-to-methanol system at VTT (Finland)
- Biomass flexibility – Access to various feedstocks
- Self-sustaining energy – SOEC reversibility enables in-situ electricity production

BeBOP TECHNICAL POTENTIAL

- Double the methanol productivity
- Achieve over 95% of carbon efficiency using polluted wood and phytoremediation biomasses mapped along Europe
- Recover high-value components from biomass residues

BeBOP FINANCIAL POTENTIAL

- Lower methanol production costs: below €250 per tonne
- Prevent over 30 million tonnes of CO₂ emission annually
- Create new market opportunities

THE BeBOP PATHWAY TO TRL9

2030/2035: First small-scale pre-commercial TRL6 (e.g. 50 MW SOEC and 10MW biomass) demonstrator

2035/2040: Large-scale (e.g. 50 MW SOEC and 100 MW biomass) FOAK/marble demonstrator

2040/2050: 10% of the European e-Methanol production shifted to BeBOP technology

MAIN GOALS: 2030/2035, 2035/2040, 2040/2050

Website: www.bebop-project.eu

Funded by the European Union

Figure 11. BeBOP's project factsheet

Figure 14. BeBOP’s Business card front and back

Figure 15. BeBOP’s postcard front and back

Figure 16. BeBOP’s Block notes

Figure 17. BeBOP’s sticker

4.5. BeBOP’s Template for Events’ Invitations

As a part of BeBOP’s communication strategy, a template for event invitations has been designed on Canva. This allows the definition of a unified framework for promoting workshops, conferences and any other project-related events. The template integrates BeBOP’s visual identity, and it is ready to be modified according to the event by adding other partners’ logos (in case of liaison activities), the title of the event, a photo, an agenda, a description and a link.

The template was used for the first time to send out the invitations for BeBOP’s First dissemination event: the Workshop on *‘Biofuels, e-fuels and sustainability strategies: research meets standardization’*, organised by UNI, in Milan on 07/10/2025².

Figure 18. BeBOP’s event invitation template and an example used for the Workshop on 07/10/2025

4.6. BeBOP’s Background for Calls

In light of the growing significance of online meetings in all areas of professional life, a branded digital background for calls was developed to ensure consistent project representation in virtual environments. This tool facilitates professional visual framing, enhances audience perception of the project and maintains brand visibility throughout digital dissemination activities.

² See: <https://www.bebop-project.eu/workshop-on-biofuels-bebop/>

Figure 19. BeBOP's background for calls

4.7. BeBOP promotional video

BeBOP's first promotional video was finalised in March 2026 and launched in all the BeBOP's communication channels on 26/03/2026, and it is now publicly available on [BeBOP's YouTube channel](#). The development of the BeBOP's promotional video is part of the consolidated strategic communication effort aimed at promoting the project's contents and innovations to the broader public and stakeholders through a simplified and visual format. Designed in English, the promotional video reflects the project's vision, objectives, and methodology through a short sketch in which BeBOP, impersonated by a MeOH molecule, introduces itself during a job interview, seeking to demonstrate its value and strengths to a recruiter.

The MP4 file is currently available in the internal project repository for partners to support its promotion and distribution among their networks and media channels. Additionally, it has also been uploaded to the [Zenodo repository](#) and the news shared on the [BeBOP website](#).

Figure 20. Screenshots of BeBOP's first promotional video

5. Website

Figure 21. Favicon image of BeBOP's website

BeBOP's website (<https://www.bebop-project.eu/>) was officially launched on December 20th, 2024, and has become the central communication and dissemination hub for the project and key instrument for transparency, engagement and lasting impacts. Hosted by the WordPress platform, it is regularly updated by the D&C leader, EUCORE, thanks also to the inputs received by all partners, ensuring that the knowledges and results generated within the project are openly available for the general public. It fully aligns with the project's visual identity and the visibility requirements of the European Commission and offers responsive access for tablets and smartphones. The website language is English, and it is structured into a Public and Private area, whose contents are described below:

- **Public Area:** The Public Area has been designed to serve as the primary hub for allowing the audience to get familiarised with the project, by providing a snapshot on the project objectives, main information, summary of the consortium and latest news and events. In particular, the Public Area is structured as follows:

Page/feature	Mission	Content
Homepage	Get people to know the main information and vision of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BeBOP's logo • Navigation bar (Home, About BeBOP, Partners, Results & Publications, Social Wall, Contacts) • Project full name and main goal • Main information including start date, duration, EU contribution, coordinator and number of partners • Top News and Events • General overview of the consortium • Subscribe to the Newsletter section • Footer including BeBOP's logo in white, EU emblem, disclaimer, contact emails and links to social accounts.
About BeBOP	Establish credibility and accountability while sharing the project background	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Structure • Project Overview • Objectives • Demonstration site • Collaboration with similar projects
Partners	Get the audience acquainted with the consortium partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map with Consortium members • Brief explanation of each partner, description of their activity within BeBOP, other collaboration/projects of the entity in the same field, link to their website and main contact person.
Results & Publications	Public dissemination of project results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public deliverables • Publications • Link to Zenodo repository • D&C Materials • Standardisation Toolkit • Newsletters
Social Wall	Get people follow the project on social media more easily	Social wall with an overview of the recent shared posts on LinkedIn and Instagram accounts
Contact	Allow users to contact the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact Form • Subscribe to the project's Newsletter

Table 1. BeBOP's Public Area structure

Homepage. The homepage (see figure below) provides user-friendly access to all sections and includes BeBOP's main image, a brief description of the project and main information, all the latest news and

events in chronological order, and a summary of BeBOP’s consortium, access to the newsletter subscription, a link to the partner area and to both social media accounts (LinkedIn and Instagram).

Figure 22. Homepage of the BeBOP’s website

About BeBOP. Accessible by the navigation bar, this important section is divided into 5 sub-sections, namely:

- **Project Structure**, including a schematic overview of all the main fields of operation and activities of the project.
- **Project overview.** This sub-section summarises in a clear and accessible manner the core concept, technological innovation and expected impacts of the BeBOP project. It serves as a bridge between high-profile project communication and more detailed technological dissemination, helping stakeholders to better understand the innovative core of the project.
- **Objectives.** It provides a clear overview of the overarching objective guiding the project and the related seven operational and scientific Specific Objectives (SO).

- **Demonstration site**, which will be populated with all the information related to the integration of the BeBOP technology at the VTT plant. This section is not yet available as the engineering of the plant is still in progress; details will be provided in the next few months.
- **Collaboration with similar projects**. This sub-section provides a list of all EU-funded projects collaborating with BeBOP in different ways.

The figure shows three screenshots of the BeBOP website. The first screenshot displays the 'Project Structure' page, which lists key milestones such as 'Gasification system and BeBOP integration', 'Design and planned implementation of SOE and syngas compression unit', and 'The Digitalization Framework of the BeBOP system'. The second screenshot shows the 'Project Overview' page, featuring a detailed flowchart of the BeBOP TR16 pilot process, from biomass input to methanol production, and lists project partners like VTT, INERIS, and Wood. The third screenshot shows the 'BeBOP Project Objectives' page, which states the overall goal of increasing biomass resource efficiency and lists specific objectives (SO1-SO7) for process development, waste minimization, and business model generation.

Figure 23. About BeBOP’s section of the website

Partners. This section comprises a summary of the consortium composition, including a map of their locations. Additionally, by clicking on the organisation logo, a pop-up appears including the description of each partner, their role in the project, other projects they work on or have worked on in the same field, contact person and a link to their website:

Figure 24. Partners section of the BeBOP's website

Results & Publications. In this section, all the public outcomes and results are listed, such as approved public deliverables, scientific publications, including a link to the [Zenodo repository](#), D&C materials available for download, such as the brochure, poster, roll-up, etc. and the place for the future Standardisation toolkit. Additionally, the previous newsletters are ready for download in PDF format, and the form to subscribe to future ones is included.

Figure 25. 'Results & Publication' section of the BeBOP's website

Social Wall. This page collects all the recent posts from BeBOP's social media accounts (LinkedIn and Instagram), which are displayed on one page for easier viewing, while allowing the audience to follow the project in a quicker and direct way.

Figure 26. BeBOP's Website social wall

Contact. The 'Contact' area enables stakeholders and the general public to interact with the consortium by providing the opportunity to submit questions or comments. In addition, the form to subscribe to the newsletter is also displayed.

Figure 27. Contact area of the website

- Partner/restricted Area.** The partners' Area is a specific interface on the BeBOP website that can only be accessed by the consortium members after logging in with their credentials. It serves as a shared repository for the final documents, especially:
 - i)** Contracts, namely Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement;
 - ii)** Budget-Finances;
 - iii)** Communication and dissemination material, including Promotional Material, templates and Logo;
 - iv)** EC reporting and
 - v)** Deliverables.

Figure 28. Partner Area

6. The BeBOP Community in Zenodo

During the first months of the project implementation, a dedicated [BeBOP's Zenodo Community](#) was created. The establishment of such a dissemination channel responds to two criticalities linked to the implementation of an EU-funded project. First and foremost, it ensures compliance with the European Union's Open Science and Open Access obligations. As also detailed in the GA, being an EU-funded initiative, the BeBOP consortium is obligated to guarantee that scientific publications and all research scientific outputs are openly accessible, properly archived and traceable; only specific derogations are foreseen under this framework. Thus, by creating the Zenodo community, a reliable, open-access repository was secured where project outputs could be systematically archived, linked to a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and made publicly available in accordance with the Granting Authority obligations.

Beyond the regulatory compliance, the creation of the BeBOP's Zenodo Community must also be read as another strategic tool put in place to foster the Communication and Dissemination of the BeBOP project outcomes, ensuring their sustainability and long-term preservation. If the project website may not be maintained after the mandatory 5 years after the project end date, Zenodo provides stable hosting and long-term archiving while ensuring accessibility to its contents beyond the project lifetime. Furthermore, it is to be noted that the Zenodo community also enhance discoverability and scientific credibility: by creating DOIs (but also linking the contents with existing DOIs) and integrating with academic indexing systems, Zenodo enables formal citation and improves the traceability of project outputs while increasing their visibility within the scientific/technical frameworks.

Figure 29. BeBOP Community in Zenodo

At the time of writing this deliverable, BeBOP Community on Zenodo collects:

- The Dataset DS.07.01b – *SOEC electrochemical characterization data*.
- The BeBOP's first promotional Video.
- The abstract and the poster entitled *Utilization of Hydrogen as an Energy Storage Vector by a Combined Reversible High Temperature Electrolysis and Compressor System Integrated with Upstream Biogas and Downstream E-Fuel Production*, presented by VTT during the 247th ECS Meeting, Montreal, Canada, on 18–22/05/2025.
- The peer-reviewed article *Progress in deep cleaning and upgrading of biomass- and waste-derived syngas for production of renewable fuels, chemicals and power published by VTT* (see also Sect.7).
- The Project's brochure (English version).
- The Dataset DS.07.02b – *Resources recovery from gasification residues*.
- The abstract presented by POLIMI at

the 11th edition of the "European Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Piero Lunghi Conference" held in Capri, Italy, on 17-19/09/2025.

- The ex-post materials of the Online Joint Workshop organised with the EU-Funded project UNITED CIRCLES (for more details see Sect. 9), including the detailed agenda, presentations and the Take away messages report, namely a summary prepared to acquaint the readers on the main important insight emerged during the event (see also Sect. 9.1).
- The ex-post materials of the First BeBOP Dissemination event, the Workshop on *'Biofuel, e-fuels and sustainability strategies: research meets standardisation'* (for more information about the event see also Sect. 8). This includes the detailed agenda, the Press release (both in Italian, as

the event was organised in Italy, and in English), all the presentations delivered by the keynote speakers and all the posters displayed and the Take away messages report of the event.

- The peer-reviewed article *Flexible integrated gasification solid oxide cell (IGSOC) plant for bio-methanol and bio-power generation* published by LUT in collaboration with POLIMI (see also Sect. 7).
- The press release of BeBOP's launch disseminated on the occasion of the project Kick-off meeting.

Following the approval of the BeBOP public deliverables submitted in RP1, also all these documents will be uploaded on Zenodo alongside any other publicly available data and results obtained by the project.

7. Publications

The table below summarises all the contributions of consortium members in peer-reviewed scientific publications, conference proceedings and abstracts during the RP1:

#	Date and partner/s involved	Type	Title and author/s	PID	Journal/conference	Open Access
1	POLIMI	Abstract in Book of Proceedings	Biomass to methanol by Breakthrough SOEC-based Process Asia Vedovi, Martina Marasi, Giulio Guandalini, Alessandro Donazzi	DOI	<i>EFCH2 2025 – Book of Proceedings</i>	Yes
2	VTT 12-16/10/2025	Abstract	Utilization of Hydrogen as an Energy Storage Vector by a Combined Reversible High Temperature Electrolysis and Compressor System Integrated with Upstream Biogas and Downstream E-Fuel Production Ville Saarinen, Jari Pennanen, Jeremias Hopsu and Olli Himanen	DOI	<i>ECS Meeting Abstracts – 247th ECS Meeting</i>	Yes
3	LUT 15/11/2025	Journal article - Peer reviewed	Flexible integrated gasification solid oxide cell (IGSOC) plant for bio-methanol and bio-power generation F. Rajaei, M. C. Romano, & J. Ritvanen	DOI	<i>Energy - Science Direct - Elsevier</i>	Yes
4	VTT 19/01/2026	Journal article - Peer reviewed	Progress in deep cleaning and upgrading of biomass- and waste-derived syngas for production of renewable fuels, chemicals and power Sikarwar VS, Pohorely M, Vuppaladadiyam AK, Frilund C, Staf M, Pfeifer C, Ronsse F, Kaviti AK, Simell P, Jeremias M	DOI	<i>Resources Chemicals and Materials - Science Direct - Elsevier</i>	Yes

Table 2. BeBOP's publications during RP1

7. Project Dissemination Events

As stated in the GA, BeBOP organised one Dissemination event during the First Reporting Period:

BeBOP First Dissemination Event - Workshop on “Biofuels, e-fuels and sustainability strategies: research meets standardization”

The First Dissemination Event was held on 07/10/2025 at the UNI premises in Milan, Italy and was organised as a Workshop. This format was chosen in order to facilitate proper knowledge transfer, maximise stakeholder engagement, and showcase research.

The objective of this interactive workshop was to address the existing disparity between research and standardisation by enhancing communication on different themes such as circularity, sustainable fuels (bio and e-fuels) and industrial symbiosis. To achieve this aim, the Workshop was structured into 2 main sessions:

- The **first session** included keynote speeches delivered by leading figures in their respective fields, including: Marco La Monica (ENEA), who delivered a presentation on circular economy and industrial symbiosis; Alessandro Marson (University of Padova) who gave his insight regarding Environmental management and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA); and Silvia Pavoni (ENI), who shared her expertise in biofuels and e-fuels.
- The **second session** was instead designed as a poster session, where 10 PhD students presented their research on topics including biofuels, e-fuels, circular economy, and environmental management. On this occasion, students, technical experts, as well as the general public attending the workshop had the valuable opportunity to engage directly, enhance the discussion and provide insights into the latest advancements in the field.

This format was considered a success in terms of communication strategy because the keynote speeches ensured scientific credibility, while the poster session showcased the emerging research diversity in the field. Furthermore, by combining the plenary reconstruction of the context with the interactive and direct dialogue, the event enabled participants to shift from simple passive listeners to active contributors.

The preparation and organisation of the Dissemination event implied the development and circulation of several dissemination and communication materials, including the BeBOP branded invitation template, the Agenda, and the circulation of a Press release. Furthermore, as a follow-up communication material after the end of the event, a takeaway message report was delivered to summarise all the key elements and insights that emerged during the event.

The take away messages report, slides and posters are available for download in the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/17514028>.

Figure 30. BeBOP Workshop flyer and photos

8. Participation in External Events

During the first 18 months of the project implementation, BeBOP's partners participated in several external events, including conferences, liaison activities and meetings with policymakers.

By attending and contributing to these external events, partners have extended the dissemination of project research and results (eventually) beyond the consortium's direct network, increasing visibility and embedding the project with wider scientific and professional communities. Furthermore, attending these external events facilitated networking and knowledge exchange, creating new opportunities for collaboration and joint initiatives while at the same time contributing to the sustainability and long-term impact of the BeBOP's results.

The table below comprises the participation of all consortium members in external events up to March 2026:

#	Partner(s) involved	Activity description	Type of activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached
1	ICODOS	ICODOS presented its involvement within the BeBOP project and the development of 3D-printed MeOH reactor during the VDI Seminar at HS Mannheim	Education and training	12/02/2025	Mannheim, Germany	Research community and students
2	ICODOS	ICODOS presented the BeBOP project activities and objectives at the RENMAD HIDRÓGENO 2025	Conference	12-13/03/2025	Zaragoza, Spain	Research communities, Industry
3	VTT	VTT presented BeBOP at the 247th ECS Meeting 2025 with a poster entitled: <i>'Utilization of Hydrogen As an Energy Storage Vector By a Combined Reversible High Temperature Electrolysis and Compressor System Integrated with Upstream Biogas and Downstream E-Fuel Production'</i>	Conference	18-22/05/2025	Montréal, Canada	Research communities, Industry
4	ICODOS	ICODOS presented the BeBOP project activities and objectives at the Start-up BW Summit 2025	Conference	02/06/2025	Stuttgart, Germany	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators, Investors
5	POLIMI	POLIMI provided a presentation entitled Biomass to methanol by Breakthrough SOEC-based Process at the EFCH2 2025 Conference	Conference	17-19/09/2025	Capri, Italy	Research communities, Industry
6	ICODOS	ICODOS presented its involvement in the BeBOP project, make audience aware of current innovative technologies in the field of	Conference	24/09/2025	Antwerp, Belgium	Research communities, Industry

#	Partner(s) involved	Activity description	Type of activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached
		Bio/E-methanol at the 12th European CO2 Utilisation Summit				
7	UNI	UNI presented the BeBOP project and future standardisation activities at CEN/TC 474 CCUS plenary meeting	Meeting	16-17/10/2025	Paris, France	Standardisation experts, Industries, Stakeholders in general
8	ICODOS	ICODOS presented its involvement in the BeBOP project, make audience aware of current innovative technologies in the field of Bio/E-methanol at the CCU Connect Conference	Conference	21/10/2025	Santander, Spain	Research communities, Industry
9	POLIMI and EUCORE	EUCORE and POLIMI attended and provided a presentation during the Food and Bio Cluster Conference organised by the EU-funded project CERNET ³	Conference and collaboration with another EU project	20-21/11/2025	Odense, Denmark	Research communities, Industry, partners from other EU-project
10	RIC	RIC provided a brief presentation of the BeBOP project during the LifeAfterCoalPL meeting series with the Polish municipality	Meeting with policymakers	21/11/2025	Kamieński, Łódzkie Voivodship, Poland	Local authorities, policy makers, entrepreneurs, citizens
11	UNI and EUCORE	UNI and EUCORE participated and provided a short overview of the BeBOP project during the CEN/TC 473 CIRCULAR ECONOMY PLENARY MEETING	Meeting	25-28/11/2025	Milan, Italy and Online	Standardisation bodies, industries and stakeholders in general
12	UNI	UNI presented the BeBOP project during the UNI/TC 057 Economia Circolare plenary meeting	Meeting	05/12/2025	Online	Italian standardisation experts, Industries, Stakeholders in general
13	ICODOS	ICODOS presented its involvement within the BeBOP project and the development of a 3D-printed MeOH reactor during the ESA BIC Baden-Württemberg meeting on Space Inspiration: Climate Resilience	Meeting	16/12/2025	Online	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators, Investors, Civil Society
14	UNI	BeBOP was showcased during a lecture on the relationship between standardisation, energy security and the transformation of the European energy system,	Lecture	09/03/2026	Bocconi University (Milan, Italy)	Students, Research community

³ The presentation entitled “Aiming at high carbon and energy efficiency in Power-and-Biomass-to-X processes: the BeBOP project” was provided by Giulio Guandalini, during the Section 2 – Technical development on CCU of the conference. For more detail on the conference see [Greenhouse gas: From Emission to Value](#)

#	Partner(s) involved	Activity description	Type of activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached
		provided by UNI at the Bocconi University (Milan)				

Table 3. Participation in external events during RP1

Among the activities summarised in the table above, it is of utmost importance to highlight the collaboration with the EU-funded [CERNET project](#) (Grant Agreement no. 101214604). This, not only helped positioning BeBOP’s communication strategy among the targeted audience, but also catalysed strategic partnership and knowledge integration across projects.

Figure 31. BeBOP at the Greenhouse gas: From emission to value Conference

9. Liaison Activities

During the first 18 months of BeBOP's implementation, considerable effort was made to organise liaison activities with other EU-funded projects. Although some contacts and discussions are still ongoing and events will take place in the coming months, the two joint events were organised during the first RP: **i)** a Joint workshop with the EU-funded project [UNITED CIRCLES](#), '**Uniting Projects and Standards for Circular Impact**' and **ii)** the thematic webinar '**Electrolysis and Gasification: Possible Synergies in Energy and Fuel Production**' organised by the CETPartnership [GeniusFuels](#) in collaboration with other two EU-Funded projects [Bio-MeGaFuel](#) and [OUTFOX](#).

9.1. Joint Workshop with the UNITED CIRCLES project

Defined within the Framework of WP4, i.e. *Circularity of the BeBOP plant and its Hubs (double level)* (M1-M18, led by ECODESIGN), the joint workshop with EU-funded H4C project [UNITED CIRCLES](#), '**Uniting Projects and Standards for Circular Impact**' was organised on 05/12/2025. The workshop aimed at fostering the collaboration between the two EU-funded projects while addressing all the following objectives:

- Provide an overview of the existing circularity standards;
- Refine a set of useful and practical performance indicators for assessing circularity, starting from those already existing by grouping and comparing them with the experience of BeBOP (i.e. a single pilot project composed of different interconnected processes) and exploring their potential application in UNITED CIRCLES project (i.e. an industrial-urban symbiosis project composed of different kind of Hubs for Circularity focused on different value chains).
- Identify the key elements that define an industrial-urban symbiosis project and clarify how a Hub for Circularity (H4C) is characterised.
- Examine how a single plant project can be positioned within an industrial symbiosis network.
- Connect experts in different fields to enhance collaboration and foster cooperation.

The Workshop was organised online on 05/12/2025 and was structured into three complementary sessions, which together ensured both technical depth and active stakeholder engagement.

- **Session 1 – Circularity Standards.** This section focused on the comparative analysis of the international standard ISO 59001 and the Italian circularity standard UNI/TS 11820. It provided participants a solid and shared reference framework, strengthening their understanding of how international and national approaches to circularity align, differ, and can be applied in practice international standard ISO 59001 and the Italian Standard for Circularity UNI/TS 11820 were analysed and compared.
- **Session 2 – Project Presentations.** This second session was dedicated to the presentation of both EU-funded projects, starting with the main figures and objectives of each one. Afterwards, BeBOP illustrated the circularity strategy and methodology used to define its process Circularity, and UNITED CIRCLES presented its circularity and developed frameworks, metrics and possible indicators, as well as challenges faced and opportunities discovered.
- **Session 3 – Key Discussions.** This final session took the form of a structured and interactive dialogue, encouraging active participation from the audience. This format proved especially effective in facilitating an in-depth discussion on critical topics, including: **a)** comparison of circularity frameworks; **b)** methodologies and inputs for addressing circularity in low-TRL innovations; **c)** identification of overlapping objectives and complementary strengths, with attention to sectoral perspectives, value-chain synergies, and geographical focus; **d)** discussion on the definition of possible guidelines; and **e)** identification of key barriers and priority areas for action related to circularity, including regulatory, technical, and financial aspects.

Overall, the workshop's structure successfully combined standardisation insights, practical project experiences, and participatory dialogue, reinforcing collaboration, mutual learning, and alignment

across initiatives. This approach significantly enhanced the event’s impact and relevance for stakeholders working on circularity at both strategic and operational levels.

Also on this occasion, all the communication and dissemination materials, including the event agenda, slides and take away messages report, are available for download in the project Zenodo community: zenodo.org/uploads/17973565.

Figure 32. Photos from the Joint Workshop

9.2. Joint Thematic Webinar organised by the CETPartnership project GeniusFuel

On 06/03/2026, BeBOP, together with two other EU-Funded projects **Bio-MeGaFuel** (G.A 101147737) and **OUTFOX** (G.A 101101439), actively participated with a presentation in the online Joint Thematic Webinar organised by the CETPartnership project **GeniusFuels**. Entitled **‘Electrolysis and Gasification: Possible Synergies in Energy and Fuel Production’**, the online webinar, attended by about 100 participants, had the aim of exploring the potential synergies between electrolysis and gasification for the sustainable production of energy and fuels and was divided into 3 core sections:

- A general introduction;
- Core presentation of the work carried out within the projects. In turn, each project representative took the floor to present their core technical and scientific activities, showcasing how electrolysis and gasification processes are the next generation of engines for boosting the green transformation of fuel and energy production.
- Interactive Discussion.

The recording and the slides presented will be shared on Zenodo by the event’s organiser.

GenusFuels
Thematic webinar
Friday 6th March 2026
15:00 (CET)

“Electrolysis and Gasification: possible synergies in energy and fuel production”

REGISTER NOW:

Agenda:
15:00 Welcome and Introduction
15:15 **GenusFuels:** “Electrolysis and Gasification a win-win relation in energy and fuel production”
15:35 **Bio-MeGaFuel:** “Bio-Methanol Production via Chemical Looping Gasification Coupled with Membrane Reactors” and “Membrane reactors for Methanol and for DME production”
15:55 **BeBOP:** “Biomass to bio/E-methanol by Breakthrough SOEC-based Process: the BeBOP Innovation”
16:15 **OUTFOX:** “Optimised Up-Scaled Technology for Next-Generation Solid Oxide Electrolysis”
16:30 Discussion
16:55 Concluding remarks

Organizers:
andrea.facchini2@unibo.it
nikola.elmstrom@unibo.it
giulia.balestra2@unibo.it

Co-funded by the European Union

BeBOP solution
BeBOP consists of a disruptive **PBLX system** integrating a **SOEC** within the syngas conditioning line for syngas upgrading through **electrochemical separation of excess oxygen**, to produce **bio/e-methanol**.

BeBOP production process

Bi-methanol conventional production process

Bi-methanol production process

The diagram illustrates the BeBOP production process, comparing it with a conventional bi-methanol production process. The BeBOP process involves biomass gasification, syngas conditioning, and electrochemical separation of excess oxygen using a SOEC (Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell) to produce bio/e-methanol. The conventional process involves biomass gasification, syngas conditioning, and methanol production without the electrochemical separation step. The BeBOP process is shown to be more efficient and sustainable.

Figure 33. Photos from the Joint Thematic Webinar

10. Social Media

In order to maximise visibility, engagement, transparency and long-term impact, the social media channels chosen for the BeBOP project to connect mainly with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and the general public at large are LinkedIn (@BeBOP Project) and Instagram (@bebop_eu_project). The LinkedIn platform was selected as the most appropriate social media to enable the project to position itself within a specific target audience, including professionals, academic and policymakers. On the other hand, Instagram complements LinkedIn by offering a visually-image driven communication channel capable of reaching younger audiences, students, early-career researchers, and the broader public. Through accessible and engaging content formats, the project can simplify complex research findings and increase inclusiveness.

Furthermore, BeBOP's online presence is also ensured with a dedicated YouTube channel, which is more widely accessible and able to enhance audience engagement and reiterate the message through audiovisual storytelling. Currently, two videos are shared: **1)** BeBOP's consortium introduction⁴ and **2)** BeBOP's first promotional video (see Sect. 4.7).

Together, all platforms: **i)** broaden audience reached beyond traditional communication channels; **ii)** strengthen BeBOP's visibility alongside with the EU funding opportunities and ensure transparency; **iii)** facilitate stakeholders' interaction and networking; **iv)** provide measurable sustainability indicators (including visualisation, likes and total number of audiences reached).

BeBOP's LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube profiles have been opened during the first months of the project and are displayed in the table below:

Social media channels	Photo
<p>LinkedIn</p>	
<p>Instagram</p>	

⁴ It is a 30-second video aimed at presenting all the partners involved in the project. It is available on the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eCXJC80w6ls>

Table 4. BeBOP social media channels

Based on the audience that each platform is aimed at reaching, contents of the posts are expected to be different in each of the accounts: while on LinkedIn posts are usually focused on the description of the plant/ specific equipment, results/publications or graphics/simulations about the activities, and organising events; Instagram media content mainly consist in photos of the current team, new entries, videos or reels explaining the activities and photos about participation in conferences or presentations. On the other hand, YouTube is devoted to a wider public, gathering explanatory videos featuring project results, key features and advantages of the BeBOP technology.

EUCORE is in charge of the overall management of the Social accounts by collecting contributions from all the beneficiaries according to the editorial plan agreed with the consortium (see Annex 2 of the D15.1, *Dissemination and Communication Plan*). The contributions are then adapted to the project's visual identity and posted. In addition to this, all partners actively contribute by providing reactions to the posts, leaving comments, and reposting on their own social accounts.

Figure 34. Examples of social media posts published during the RP1

At the time of writing this deliverable, a total of 37 posts and 9 stories have been published on BeBOP's Instagram account and 39 posts on the project's LinkedIn account. In addition, partners actively make posts about BeBOP's works and activities in their own social accounts. The table below summarises the contributions from each of the partners to communicate BeBOP to the public:

#	Partner	Date	Description of the post	Social media channel	Link to post
1	ICODOS	01/11/2024	Launch of the BeBOP project	LinkedIn	Link
2	EUCORE	19/11/2024	Project launch	LinkedIn	Link
3	INERIS	20/11/2024	Project launch	LinkedIn	Link
4	POLIMI	20/12/2024	BeBOP cited and introduced in Radio podcast	LinkedIn	Link
5	ECODESIGN	03/03/2025	Organisation of the First Circularity Workshop	LinkedIn	Link
6	ELCOGEN and ELCOY	21/07/2025	Elcogen's involvement in BeBOP	LinkedIn	Link
7	UNI	08/09/2025	Promotion of the BeBOP First Dissemination Event	LinkedIn	Link
8	ECODESIGN	15/10/2025	Promotion of the BeBOP Annual meeting and 6 th Circularity workshop	LinkedIn	Link
9	UNI	10/03/2026	BeBOP was presented during a lecture on standards at the University of Bocconi	LinkedIn	Link

Table 5. Partners social media posts about BeBOP

11. Press Releases and Other Mass Media

Another important pillar of a winning communication and dissemination strategy is BeBOP's presence in general media, including press releases, online articles, website mentions, podcasts, and television. General media engagement is not an auxiliary task but a fundamental pillar of BeBOP's D&C strategy as it minimises the gap between high-level research and the European public, ensuring visibility and awareness while maximising the impact and exploitation of project results.

The table below provides a summary of all communication activities carried out during the RP1, including press releases, articles, mentions on websites, participation in events, and podcast quotations:

#	Activity name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
1	Website Post	News at the RIC website on project launch (English version, Polish version)	07/10/2024	Website	Business partners, research communities, and industry
2	Website Post	ICODOS published on its website the press release on the project launch	01/11/2024	Website/Press release	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
3	Powertrain magazine article	Press release on the BeBOP launch published in a magazine, and LinkedIn and Facebook posts	18/11/2024	Media Article + Social Media	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
4	Website Post	News and press release on the BeBOP launch published on the ECODESIGN website	18/11/2024	Website/Press release	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
5	Website Post	Press release on the BeBOP launch published on the INERIS website	18/11/2024	Website/Press release	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors, citizens
6	Website Post	Press release on the BeBOP launch published on the EUCORE website	19/11/2024	Website/Press release	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors, citizens
7	Website Post	Press release on the BeBOP Kick-off meeting published on the INERIS website	20/11/2024	Website/Press release	General public
8	Website Post	News on the BeBOP Kick-off meeting published on the POLIMI website	04/12/2024	Website/Press release	General public
9	Newsletter	BeBOP description and launch described in the UNI newsletter	12/12/2024	Newsletter	Technical experts, industry, Research organizations, Italian authorities, Civil society, Associations and NGOs
10	Website Post	News on the BeBOP launch published on the UNI website	12/12/2024	Website/Press release	Technical experts, industry, Research organizations, Italian authorities, Civil society, Associations and NGOs
11	Radio Campaign	Matteo Romano, BeBOP Scientific Coordinator, describes BeBOP on Radio 24	12/12/2024	Radio interview	General public, Business partners, research communities, industry
12	Online Media Articles	Article: From AI-driven compliance to wastewater-based fuel: 10 key announcements from Techarena 2025	25/02/2025	Media Article	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors, Civil Society
13	Website	BeBOP is included among the collaborating projects of the CO ₂ Value Europe website	04/03/2025	Website	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners,

#	Activity name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
					Innovators, Investors, General Public
14	Website	BeBOP is cited in the UNI web article on Green transition and the role of technical norms	12/03/2025	Website	Technical experts, industry, research organizations, Italian authorities, civil society, associations and NGOs
15	Website	ECODESIGN published a news on the organisation of the First BeBOP Circularity Workshop	21/03/2025	Website	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
16	Website	BeBOP is presented on LUT website	28/03/2025	Website	Research communities, industry, business partners, innovators, investors, national authorities, regional authorities, local authorities, civil society, citizens, specific end user communities
17	Website	BeBOP is included among the ELCOGEN partnership projects	07/04/2025	Website	Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
18	A.SPIRE Newsletter	News about BeBOP at the 32nd edition of the ASPIRE Newsletter	15/04/2025	Newsletter	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
29	Website	ECODESIGN promoted the organisation of the 3 rd Circularity Workshop	07/05/2025	Website	Industry, SMEs, consultants, research, business partners and innovators
20	Exhibition at the World Hydrogen Summit & Exhibition	ELCOGEN promoted BeBOP during the World Hydrogen Summit & Exhibition in Rotterdam (The Netherlands)	20-22/05/2025	Exhibitions	Research communities, industry, business partners, innovators, investors, national authorities, regional authorities, local authorities
21	Website	ECODESIGN published the following news on its website: / BeBOP Project Workshop in Mannheim Highlights Circularity Potentials of Methanol Synthesis	30/05/2025	Website	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
22	Website	Promotion of the BeBOP first Dissemination Event on UNI website	04/09/2025	Website	Technical experts, industry, research organizations, Italian authorities, civil society, associations and NGOs
23	A.SPIRE Newsletter	Communication of the first BeBOP dissemination event in the 34 th ASPIRE Newsletter	18/09/2025	Newsletter	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
24	Website post	ASPIRE shared information on the BeBOP Dissemination event	07/10/2025	Website	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
25	Website Post	ICODOS published on its website the press release on the Dissemination event	08/10/2025	Website/Press release	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
26	Website	UNI promoted via its channels the First BeBOP Dissemination event	09/10/2025	Website	Technical experts, industry, research organizations, Italian authorities, civil society, associations and NGOs
27	Website Post	ECODESIGN published news on its website about the Dissemination event	15/10/2025	Website	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors
28	Website	BeBOP is listed among the FLEXBY partner projects	11/02/202	Website	Research Communities, Industry, Business Partners, Innovators, Investors

Table 6. Summary of BeBOP's Communication activities during RP1

12. Newsletters

As detailed in the BeBOP GA, issuing bi-annual newsletters is another essential tool in the D&C strategy. Unlike social media posts or event-based outreach, which are often episodic and algorithm-dependent, newsletters are a direct and subscription-based communication channel. This tool enables the consortium to reach the targeted audience in a consistent and controlled manner, strengthening the affiliation with the audience at the same time, and ensuring that project developments are systematically communicated rather than randomly encountered online. Furthermore, newsletters are also strategically valuable for translating technical outputs into an accessible narrative highlighting milestones, results and general implementation progress in a format that is both structured in its contents, as well as, audience-oriented. In this context, during the past months, two issues of the newsletter were successfully disseminated in April 2025 and February 2026.

The [first issue of the Newsletter](#) provides a general overview of the project and a summary of the activities performed during the first months of the project. It includes the project kick-off meeting held in Milan, Italy, in November 2024 and the first circularity workshop organised by the ECODESIGN partner at the VTT premises in Finland in February 2025. It also includes information on the BeBOP launch in the media, providing direct links to the Radio 24 podcast and Powertrain magazine article. Finally, it provides insights into future activities for which active participation in the project is envisaged.

The [second issue of the Newsletter](#) was finalised and sent out in February 2026. Following the same structure as the first newsletter, it includes details of all the main BeBOP appointments from April to October 2025, including the first Dissemination Event and Annual Meeting held in October 2025, and the Joint Workshop organised with the UNITED CIRCLES project in December 2025. In addition to information on the media presence of BeBOP, the newsletter also includes direct links to two scientific publications and a summary of the technical implementation of the activities. This summary includes a link to a separate [online document](#) detailing the scientific achievements addressed within the first 17 months, broken down by specific scientific implementation. Finally, it provides insights into future activities in which BeBOP involvement is envisaged.

Both newsletters are available for download on the website.

Figure 35. BeBOP's first and second newsletters and upcoming events distribution

Finally, a **third distribution** was disseminated at the beginning of March, including the key upcoming events in which BeBOP will be involved up to May 2026, such as the thematic webinar organised by the Geniusfuel project, the organisation of a parallel session during the EUBCE 2026 conference in May, and a joint symposium organised by the EU-funded project FLEXBY involving six other EU-funded projects within the scope of e-fuel and sustainability, including BeBOP also this last distribution is currently available on the **BeBOP website**.

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